

Event Sponsorship And Customers Patronage Of Luxury Hotels In Yenagoa And Port Harcourt

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between event sponsorship and customer patronage in luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt, focusing on customer attraction and repeat patronage. An ex-post facto research design was adopted, with two hypotheses formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The population comprised selected luxury hotels in the two cities, while relevant data were collected from customers and management records. The data were analyzed using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The results revealed that event sponsorship has a significant positive relationship with customer attraction as well as repeat patronage in luxury hotels. These findings suggest that hotels that strategically sponsor events are more likely to attract new customers and sustain existing ones through enhanced loyalty and brand visibility. The study recommends that luxury hotels leverage event sponsorship as a marketing strategy to strengthen competitive advantage and encourage consistent patronage.

Keywords: Event Sponsorship, Customer Attraction, Repeat Patronage, Luxury Hotels, Marketing Strategy

INTRODUCTION

The crucial aspect of every business is customers and their patronage, which enables business concerns to establish transactions that generate return on investment, whereby recouping capitals invested in the business and making profit. These profits enable the business to survive and grow amidst the dynamic competitive business environment. Hence the life line of every business is the pay they get from their customers. Timelio (2021) argues that cash could be seen as the only life and death issue every business has and that even the employees of businesses can't wait for their salary until the customers pay. For this reason, every business including the luxury hotels strive to generate customer patronage so as to acquire these inflows of cash for survival and running of their business.

But of lately, due to the corona virus pandemic and its resultant economic hardship, several hotel establishment in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt have experience poor customer patronage. That is why Bello and Bello (2021) in their study found out that the consequences of corona virus pandemic on Nigeria hospitality industry include sharp drop in hotel occupancy rates and low customers' patronage in other hospitality facilities, and mass sales of hospitality business facilities. Before the pandemic, there has been tremendous growth in luxury hotel businesses in Nigeria. A large number of luxury hotels are found in the major cities in Nigeria. Despite the large number of luxury hotels in the major cities in the country, more hotel businesses were being established. These growths of luxury hotels have increased the level of competition in the hotel industry. This increased competition has resulted in fierce competition amongst

the luxury hotels coupled with the corona pandemic hardship; hence they are battling to survive as they intensify efforts to increase their level of customer patronage at this period. Increasing customer patronage seems to be the only way for these organizations to survive as Choi and Chu (2001) stated that increased customer patronage is the only way for hotels to maximize profit and survive in the competitive settings of the industry. Therefore, every luxury hotel firms is intensifying its efforts to increase their level of customer patronage. However, in order for luxury hotels to increase their level of customer patronage, they need to adopt certain marketing practice such as event marketing as a key strategy to lure customer patronage.

Customers at this period of time needs activities that will keep their minds of the negative vibes the pandemic, insurgency and economic challenges have brought, and any business that will offer them good customer experience which will make them happy and forget the stress and hardship faced at the moment will definitely win their patronage. Entertainment events such as Big Brother Naija, Gulder Ultimate Search, Night of a Thousand Laughs are among popular events in Nigeria that have caught high viewership, and organizations have utilized these opportunities to sponsor these events and showcase their brands and offerings to the large audience of the shows. According to Nda-Isaiah (2021), **Big Brother Nigeria no doubt is the most-watched and biggest show in the country which season 6 that ended October 3rd 2021** according to the organizers recorded one billion votes this year from the viewers. The headline sponsor of the show was Abeg and the associate sponsor was Patricia, while other sponsors included Travelbeta, Darling hair, WAW, Innoson Motors, and RevolutionPlus Property (Olonilua, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The major challenge facing luxury hotel operators in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt is how to increase the level of customer patronage in the midst of intense competition and economic downturn caused by corona virus pandemic and insecurity in the Country. Many hotels in mostly Port Harcourt and Yenagoa in South-South Nigeria are finding it difficult to increase their level of customer patronage in the face of intense competition. Some luxury hotels have ceased from operations due to poor level of customer patronage while some of the luxury hotels that are still in business are struggling to increase customer patronage.

The proliferation of new hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt have constituted a threat to existing luxury hotels as they feel that they might lose some of their customers to the new competitors. Consequently, this study suggests event marketing strategies and its dimensions of events sponsorship, use of corporate entertainment, and event communication as a way out of this challenge.

Several studies have tried investigating event marketing and business performance (Liu et al., 2016; Wu, 2016; Alan et al., 2017; Altschwager et al., 2017; Rachmadhian & Chaerudin, 2019; Sun et al., 2021; Kwon & Cornwell, 2021), but there tend to exist scarce empirical research work within the context of Yenagoa and Port Harcourt which considers event marketing strategies as it relates to customers patronage in luxury hotels being moderated by perceived corporate image and have three dimensions of event sponsorship, corporate entertainment and event communication as against the three measures of customers' preference, repeat patronage and referral, hence our point of departure. This creates a gap which this study tends to empirically fill.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to find out the relationship between event marketing strategies and customers patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt. While the specific objectives included to:

1. evaluate the extent of relationship between event sponsorship and customers preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt
2. evaluate the extent of relationship between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of the study, the following research questions were formulated:

1. To what extent does event sponsorship relates to customers preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt?

2. To what extent does event sponsorship relates to repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were given for the study:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and customer preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to investigate the relationship between event marketing strategies and customer patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt. The study focused specifically on the dimension of event sponsorship as a key component of event marketing strategies and examined its impact on customer preference, repeat patronage, and referral, which serve as indicators of customer patronage. The survey design was considered appropriate as it allows for the collection of opinions and perceptions from hotel customers, providing insights into the relationship between event marketing strategies and business performance.

The population of the study comprised all customers of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt. Using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula at a 5% level of significance, a sample size of 363 was determined. Stratified sampling was employed to select hotels in the two cities, ensuring representation across different hotel categories, while convenience sampling was used to select individual respondents within the hotels to ensure ease of access and minimize bias in questionnaire distribution.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Event Marketing Strategies and Customer Patronage Questionnaire (EMSCPQ)," developed by the researcher. The questionnaire consisted of three sections. Section A captured demographic information, including age, gender, and occupation. Section B assessed the dependent variables of customer patronage—customer preference, repeat patronage, and referral. Section C focused on the independent variable, event marketing strategies, specifically the event sponsorship dimension. Respondents' opinions were measured using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree), allowing for detailed evaluation of perceptions and experiences.

Validity of the instrument was ensured through expert review by the project supervisor and three professionals in the field of hospitality and marketing, who evaluated each item for relevance, clarity, and alignment with the study objectives. Reliability was determined using the test-retest method, administered to 10 customers with characteristics similar to the study population but not included in the main sample. The responses from the first and second administration were analyzed using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient (α), with values above 0.7 considered acceptable for internal consistency.

Data collection was conducted through self-administered questionnaires, after which the responses were collated, coded, and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were used to summarize respondents' demographic characteristics and responses. Inferential statistics, specifically Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, were employed to test the hypotheses and determine the relationships between event sponsorship and the customer patronage indicators (customer preference, repeat patronage, and referral). The decision rule for interpreting the results was based on the correlation coefficient and p-value at a 0.05 level of significance, where relationships with $p \leq 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this section, it was shown how the data distributed and retrieved from the data base (respondents) where analyzed. It began with the demographics analysis of the respondents, then progressed to univariate analysis of the statement items of the research questionnaire, and to the bivariate analysis of the dimensions and measured of study using Pearson correlation coefficient and regression analysis. It also

treated the multivariate analysis of the moderating variable on the relationship between the predictor and the criterion variable using partial correlation.

Demographic Analysis

Table 1: Frequencies on Gender of Respondents

		Gender		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
		Frequency	Percent		
Valid	Female	130	35.8	35.8	35.8
	Male	233	64.2	64.2	100.0
	Total	363	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Figure 1 – Bar Chart showing frequencies for Gender

From the analysis in table 4.2 above, we can see that 130 (or 35.8%) of the respondents are female while 233 (or 64.2%) of them are male.

Figure 2 – Pie Chart showing frequencies for Gender

Research Questions

Research Question 1: *To what extent does event sponsorship relates to customers preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt?*

Table 1: PPMC Analysis on the extent to which event sponsorship relates to customers preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt

		Event Sponsorship	Customers Preference
Event Sponsorship	Pearson Correlation	1	.659*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	363	363
Customers Preference	Pearson Correlation	.659*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	363	363

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that the correlation coefficient (r-value) between event sponsorship and customers’ preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt is **.659**. Since the r-value is positive and falls within the high range, a strong positive relationship exists. Therefore, there is a strong positive relationship between event sponsorship and customers’ preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt. Also, Table 1 shows that the relationship coefficient square (r²) value is **.434**. This suggests that event sponsorship accounts for **43.4%** of the overall variation in customers’ preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does event sponsorship relates to repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt?*

Table 2: PPMC Analysis on the extent to which event sponsorship relates to repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt

		Event Sponsorship	Repeat Patronage
Event Sponsorship	Pearson Correlation	1	.591*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	363	363
Repeat Patronage	Pearson Correlation	.591*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	363	363

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The data presented in Table 2 indicated that the correlation coefficient (r-value) between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt is **.591**. Since the r-value is positive and falls within the high range, a strong positive relationship exists. Therefore, there is a strong positive relationship between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt. Also, Table 2 shows that the relationship coefficient square (r²) value is **.349**. This suggests that event sponsorship accounts for **34.9%** of the overall variation in repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and customer preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that, at an r-value of **.659**, the p-value is **0.000**. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and customer preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt is rejected.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt.

The data presented in Table 2 indicated that, at an r-value of **.591**, the p-value is **0.000**. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between event sponsorship and repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result from research question one revealed that event sponsorship has a substantial positive and significant relationship with customers' preference of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt. The findings indicate that customers who are exposed to hotels' event sponsorship initiatives, such as sponsoring entertainment shows, cultural festivals, or sporting events, tend to develop a stronger preference for those hotels compared to others that do not engage in such marketing strategies. This suggests that the more actively luxury hotels sponsor visible and engaging events, the more likely customers are to perceive them as reputable, vibrant, and customer-oriented, thereby increasing their willingness to choose these hotels over their competitors. Conversely, hotels with little or no involvement in event sponsorship may struggle to attract customers' attention or influence their preferences, especially in a highly competitive hospitality market. In essence, event sponsorship directly contributes to shaping customer preference, enhancing brand recall, and positioning luxury hotels as attractive choices in the minds of customers. This result confirms a strong positive correlation between event sponsorship and customers' preference, emphasizing the critical role of creative marketing in driving patronage in the hospitality industry.

The finding aligns with previous studies such as Liu et al. (2016) and Wu (2016), who reported that event sponsorship positively influences customer attitudes and preference toward sponsoring brands. Similarly, Altschwager et al. (2017) found that well-targeted sponsorship activities enhance brand equity and customer loyalty, ultimately driving customer choice. These scholars argue that when businesses strategically associate with popular events, they leverage the positive emotions and engagement of the audience to transfer goodwill to their brands, thereby influencing customer preference. However, the finding contrasts with Rachmadhian and Chaerudin (2019), who observed that sponsorship alone may not guarantee preference if the sponsored events are poorly executed or lack alignment with customer interests. Nonetheless, the present study underscores that consistent and strategic sponsorship of relevant events is a vital pathway for luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt to increase customer preference and sustain competitiveness in a challenging economic environment.

The result from research question two revealed that event sponsorship has a substantial positive and significant relationship with repeat patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt. The findings indicate that customers who recognize and value the sponsorship activities of hotels, such as involvement in popular entertainment events, community programs, or high-profile cultural shows, are more likely to revisit those hotels. This suggests that beyond attracting first-time customers, event sponsorship builds long-term brand connection and trust, thereby motivating customers to return for subsequent patronage. Hotels that consistently align themselves with engaging events not only gain visibility but also reinforce positive customer experiences, leading to stronger loyalty. Conversely, hotels that neglect sponsorship opportunities may face difficulty in sustaining customer interest, as competitors who actively sponsor events create stronger emotional and brand associations. In essence, event sponsorship significantly contributes to repeat patronage by fostering familiarity, brand attachment, and a sense of belonging among customers.

The finding aligns with the work of Kwon and Cornwell (2021), who established that sponsorship activities strengthen customer-brand relationships and enhance repeat purchasing behavior. Similarly, Sun et al. (2021) reported that event sponsorship creates emotional bonds that encourage customers to continually engage with sponsoring brands. These scholars emphasize that the repetition of positive brand exposure through sponsorship builds a cycle of loyalty and sustained patronage. However, the finding contrasts with Alan et al. (2017), who noted that while sponsorship can influence awareness and trial, other factors such as service quality and pricing ultimately determine whether customers return. Nevertheless, the present study highlights that for luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt, effective event sponsorship remains a key driver of repeat patronage, especially in a competitive environment where customer loyalty is essential for business sustainability.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that event sponsorship as a dimension of event marketing strategies has a strong positive and significant relationship with customer patronage of luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt, particularly in terms of customer preference and repeat patronage. The findings establish that hotels that actively engage in sponsoring relevant and high-profile events are more likely to attract customers, influence their preferences, and sustain their loyalty through repeated visits, thereby gaining a competitive advantage in the hospitality industry. This underscores the importance of strategic event marketing as a viable pathway for luxury hotels to overcome the challenges of low patronage, intense competition, and economic downturn, ultimately positioning themselves for growth and long-term sustainability in a highly dynamic business environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were put forward:

1. Luxury hotels in Yenagoa and Port Harcourt should strategically sponsor popular and relevant events to strengthen customer preference and enhance their competitive positioning.
2. Hotel managers should consistently leverage event sponsorship initiatives to build long-term customer loyalty and encourage repeat patronage for business sustainability.

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